

Angelo Leogrando^{1*}°

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

Long-Term Unemployment in Europe

It decreased by an average of 27.9% between 2009 and 2022

Eurostat calculates the value of long-term unemployment. The indicator measures the share of the economically active population aged between 15 and 74 who has been unemployed for 12 months or more. The unemployed are defined as all persons who were out of work during the reference week, were currently available for work and were actively looking for work in the past four weeks or had already found a job to start within the next three months. The period of unemployment is defined as the duration of a job search, or as the period of time since the last job. The economically active population includes both employed and unemployed.

Ranking of European countries for the value of long-term unemployment in 2022. Greece is in first place for the value of long-term unemployment in 2022 with a value of 7.7 units, followed by Spain with a value of 5.0 and from Italy with an amount of 4.6 units. In the middle of the table are Latvia with a value of 2.0 units, followed by Sweden with a value of 1.9 units, and Slovenia with a value of 1.7 units. The Czech Republic and Norway close the ranking with a value of 0.6 units, followed by Denmark with an amount of 0.5 units.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the percentage change in long-term unemployment between 2009 and 2022. Cyprus ranks first by the value of the percentage change in long-term unemployment between 2009 and 2022 with a change of 283.33% equal to an amount of 1.7 units, followed by Greece with a value of 113.89% equal to an amount of 4.1 units and by Italy with a value of 24.32% equal to an amount of 0.9 unit. In the middle of the ranking are the Netherlands with a value of -22.22% equal to an amount of -0.2 units, followed by Belgium with an amount of -28.13% equal to a value of -0.9 units, and from Lithuania with a value of -30.3% equal to an amount of -1.00 units. The Czech Republic closes the ranking with a change equal to an amount of -70.00% equal to an amount of -1.4 units, followed by Hungary with an amount of -70.00% equal to an amount of -2.8 units, followed by Germany with a change equal to an amount of -70.59% equal to an amount of -2.4 units. Between 2009 and 2022 the value of long-term unemployment decreased by an amount equal to -0.81071 units equal to a value of -27.92%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithms optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two different clusters are identified, namely:

- Cluster 1: Spain, Slovakia, Croatia, Greece, Portugal, Italy, Bulgaria, Latvia;
- Cluster 2: Sweden, Finland, Czech Republic, Germany, Austria, Luxembourg, Netherlands, France, Denmark, Malta, Romania, Poland, Norway, Belgium, Hungary, Slovenia, Estonia, Cyprus, Lithuania, Ireland.

¹Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrando.cultore@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

From a clustering point of view, it appears that the median value of Cluster 1-C1 is equal to an amount of 3.4 units, while the median value of Cluster 2-C2 is equal to an amount of 1.3 units. From the point of view of geographical representation, there is a contrast between the area of Northern Europe which has a low level of long-term unemployment and the area of Southern Europe which instead has levels of long-term unemployment higher.

Network analysis with Euclidean distance. A network analysis using the Euclidean distance is presented below. A complex network structure and a simplified network structure are identified. The complex network structure has the following characteristics:

- Finland has a connection with Sweden in the amount of 0.34 units, and with Austria in the amount of 0.48 units;
- Sweden has a connection with Finland for the amount of 0.34 units, and with Austria for the amount of 0.45 units;
- Austria has a connection with Finland for the amount of 0.48 units, with Sweden for the amount of 0.45 units, and with Luxembourg for the amount of 0.19 units;
- Luxembourg has a connection with Austria worth 0.19 units.

There is a complex network structure constituted as follows:

- Norway and Denmark have a connection amounting to 0.45 units.

Conclusions. The long-term unemployment rate grew on average in Europe between 2009 and 2014 from an amount of 2.90% up to a value of 5.46%. However, starting from 2013 and until 2022, the value of the long-term unemployment rate decreased from an amount of 5.28% to a value of 2.09%. The trend in the long-term unemployment rate shows the effect of the 2009 crisis which was reabsorbed only after about 13 years. This condition highlights the difficulty of the European economic system in reacting to the adverse effects of the crisis. However, there is a significant difference between Southern Europe and Northern Europe. Indeed, long-term unemployment in Southern Europe tends to be around 260% of the value of long-term unemployment in Northern Europe. This condition highlights the low efficiency of labor markets in southern Europe, especially in Greece, Italy, and Spain. However, it is very likely that the shadow economy, the illegal economy and the inefficiency of statistical reporting tend to overestimate long-term unemployment in Southern European countries. In any case, the presence of high levels of long-term unemployment raises the question of the need to intervene with economic policy instruments capable of offering both adequate unemployment benefits, citizenship and inclusion allowances or income, as well as training courses for the re-skilling of unemployed workers.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Tasso Medio di Disoccupazione di Lungo Periodo nei Paesi Europei. Fonte Eurostat

C1>C2

